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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP9 – Outreach activities for impact enhancement

D9.4 – ACCEPT dissemination and communication plan and activity report v3

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Abbreviations

DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DoW	Description of Work
DR	Demand Response
EC	European Commission
IPR	Intellectual property rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PP	Project Partner
SE	Stakeholder Ecosystem
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
UG	User Group
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable represents the 3rd version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan for the ACCEPT project, including an updated schedule for the dissemination and communication activities, the different dissemination material produced, as well as a documentation of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by all the project partners until M30 of the project. In addition to the comprehensive monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities, this report also includes a clear evaluation of the communication performance based on KPI's that have been established in the first version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan. Through these indicators a qualitative and quantitative evaluation was carried out and is represented in this version of the DCP.

This report is delivered in the context of **WP9 - Outreach activities for impact enhancement** and contains the general Dissemination and Communication Strategy with strategic elements that need to be considered as well as some focus groups that are of special importance. Within the Communication and Dissemination Plan, an overview of the dissemination and communication activities to be carried out within the project is given, which communication channels are used and which supporting materials have been created with a corporate project design ensuring a successful and consistent external impact of the project. This deliverable also describes how partners and pilot regions are collaborating to allow a successful dissemination and communication process and a smooth operation of the living labs. It also explains which communication procedures should be followed when reporting or disseminating an activity.

This deliverable also includes the monitoring and documentation process of all the activities carried out by the project partners, moreover containing KPI's for the constant evaluation of the performance and target deployment.

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Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the document

This report provides the third and updated version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) describing the communication strategy, activities, and implementation instruments of the ACCEPT project. It gives an overview about the dissemination tools, the promotional materials, ways of communication and dissemination of the project activities, results and outcomes to the end-users, stakeholders and also to the general public. The DCP describes different communication strategies, means and materials to address dissemination (tailored to the needs of the main target groups) and communication (to a wider audience). A continuous monitoring process is implemented to enable the assessment of the results and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities providing regular feedback to the effectiveness of the strategy.

1.2. Structure of deliverable

This report is an updated version of the Dissemination and Communication plan and represents the third version of a series of connected deliverables. The DCP will be updated three times during the project lifetime (see Figure 1). The document includes updated information on all communication and dissemination activities and additional material, established networks with relevant projects, platforms and associations, evaluation of communication and dissemination performance and impact, as well as updated KPI's.

Figure 1: Overview of Deliverables in Task T9.1-Dissemination and communication plan definition

This document represents the third version of the DCP and describes in detail the tasks that have been undertaken to continuously update and manage the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy and planning of activities. This will also further be highlighted in chapter two and twelve of the document.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

The dissemination and communication activities in general have a special status with the relationship to other tasks and work packages, as they are related to (almost) every other project activity (see Figure 2). Those activities are part of the horizontal project phase, composing all the horizontal supporting activities namely i) dissemination and communication (WP9), where specifically targeted communication and dissemination strategies/actions (e.g. website, publications, conferences, workshops, etc.) will be designed and conducted by the project partners; ii) exploitation (WP8) where all the necessary activities will be performed to enable commercial and research exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes to maximize the project impact during and after its lifetime and iii) project management (WP1) consisting of all administrative, financial and data management activities as well as the overall quality assurance.

Figure 2: ACCEPT Work Package interdependency Graph

There are also some particular connections with this task/deliverable and other tasks and work packages within the project.

- Results and insights drawn from tasks of WP3 and WP8, where the consortium will generate recommendations regarding policy/regulation as well as market structures, will be translated in policy briefs to facilitate efficient communication with policy makers.
- The DCP covers only dissemination and communication within ACCEPT, while another related activity, namely the exploitation of the project results, is addressed in task T8.2 - Exploitation strategy and IPR management.

2. Strategy

2.1. Overall dissemination and communication strategy

This section presents the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication strategy, which precedes a more in-depth description of the communication activities to be implemented in the course of the project. The major focus of the ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication plan (DCP) is to ensure that the project activities and outcomes are widely spread among the appropriate audiences, at appropriate times, via appropriate methods, as well as to identify potential contributors to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of ACCEPT outcomes, encouraging their participation on a systematic and regular basis.

Basically, the central questions to be addressed by any dissemination and communication strategy are:

- To whom to communicate? (Audience)
- What to communicate? (Messages)
- How to communicate? (Methods and Time)

At this point, it should also be pointed out that the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication activities are intrinsically linked to the exploitation of the project results. The efficient publicity and the wide exposure of the project activities and results to targeted stakeholders and media would facilitate the use of these results beyond the project's lifetime and thus, would increase the project impact.

Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation – it's all about reaching out to various audiences. However, the goals behind those outreach activities are different. The EC published an overview, which helps to distinguish between these related and connected outreach frameworks (see Figure 3):

Figure 3: Difference between Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation¹

While the aspects of dissemination and communication will be covered in the DCP, aspects of exploitation will be separately covered in T8.2 and the corresponding Deliverables.

Above, the central questions to be addressed by this dissemination and communication strategy are mentioned. What is missing, however, is the question related in relation to the purpose – the “why?”. Why to communicate, why to disseminate, what is the motivation behind these activities and which goals do we wish to achieve? These goals differ for dissemination and communication actions; the most important ones are illustrated in the following section.

¹ European Commission s.a. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. Why they all matter and what is the difference? Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

2.1.1. Objectives

Prior to every communication or dissemination activity there is a motivation or goal, we would like to achieve with such an activity. Whether important project results will be shown to a large audience at an international event or if a community recruitment activity is posted on social media – the general objective is to make the project's work and achievements visible. Having this general goal in mind, further – more detailed – objectives can be formulated:

- Create public awareness, understanding and interest about the scope, objectives and results of the project
- Address all the stakeholders of the project with specific and valuable knowledge and solutions
- Engage the stakeholders and drive them to adopt and implement the project results

2.1.2. Approach

At the beginning of drafting of a strategy it is important to have a clear picture of the basis and foundation, from which this development will start. A good dissemination and communication strategy is always a process in development, as it is important to constantly monitor, re-evaluate and, if necessary, adapt the strategy and the planned actions.

For a successful implementation of a dissemination and communication strategy the choice of the correct dissemination plan and the means to be used for is essential. Dissemination activities will target the public, academic and industrial areas and the target groups cover a wide variety of sectors from high-level to low-level stakeholders, which shows the need for different approaches within the dissemination plan per target group.

In addition, it is important to choose the right dissemination channels, as the usage of social media and the web can also play an important role, apart from the dissemination of the project, promoting possible future cooperation but even more in providing real feedback over the circulation of project and valuable participants' data bank for future projects. The aforementioned methods & channels will prepare for scaling-up of the project solutions and will allow for getting the market ready for their use.

For the general approach it is important:

- To clearly define contributors and relevant target audiences within ACCEPT
- To choose the right supports & channels

All project partners will contribute to the communication and dissemination activities using their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects. The project consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes, academia and energy cooperatives to enable to reach a diversified audience. The communication and dissemination activities and experiences by partners will be carried out on various channels (website, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, electronic/printed newsletter, press release, etc.). Within the first phase of the ACCEPT project a questionnaire (Project Partner Form) was created to identify the communication channels used by the PPs in order to plan dissemination activities accordingly.

A dissemination and communication activity report will be compiled regularly to assess D&C results and identify ad hoc contingency measures if needed.

2.1.3. Communication timeline

The ACCEPT communication strategy timeline is structured in three main phases (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: ACCEPT communication strategy

- Phase 1 – Initial awareness phase aims at
 - agreeing upon the communication strategy and future activities
 - creating initial awareness in markets, communities & citizens related with the project’s objectives and scope
- Phase 2 – Targeted awareness market phase aims at
 - Creating “targeted awareness” regarding ACCEPT technologies focusing on key players (e.g., communities) and citizens
 - informing the target market about its technological benefits
- Phase 3 – Strategic phase aims at
 - maximizing target market awareness regarding the ACCEPT solution
 - contributing to ensure the project sustainability and full exploitation

As it is visible from Figure 4, the project already reached phase 2, focusing on the creation of targeted awareness material and related plans on how to reach the key players as well as the citizens. As a first step the creation of a respective info-campaign was started.

2.1.4. Roles and responsibilities

The European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing (EEE) is the organization leading the dissemination and communication within ACCEPT. EEE will prepare and update the ACCEPT Dissemination & Communication Plan (DCP) and coordinate activities throughout the overall project duration.

However, all partners will use their own channels, industrial partnerships, standardization activities and long-standing experience in EU funded projects, to contribute to dissemination and communication activities.

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The consortium is formed by a well-balanced group of industrial companies, SMEs, research institutes, academia and energy cooperatives and it is able to reach a diversified audience.

In addition to the general dissemination and communication approach, special attention will be paid to two focus areas. Firstly, the Living Labs need dedicated dissemination activities and strategies to reach out to the end users and local stakeholders in each pilot region. This pilot-oriented dissemination and communication approach is defined in T3.1 and will be described in the corresponding Deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D3.4). SIN as leading organization of these activities is therefore foreseen as Living Lab coordinator for dedicated dissemination and communication activities, as shown in Table 1.

Secondly, the exchange with other projects – either directly or via networks (e.g., BRIDGE Initiative) – needs special attention throughout the project. HYPERTECH will be the coordinator of related actions to ensure a continuous cooperation with similar projects and important networks. This will be done as part of the activities in WP10 and reported in the corresponding Deliverables (D10.1, D10.2, D10.3, D10.4). This coordinative role is also assigned in the following table.

Table 1: Roles and coordination of responsibilities in the ACCEPT dissemination and communication activities

Team member	Role	Contact
Manfred Hotwagner	Dissemination and communication coordinator Responsible for all communication and dissemination activities in the project	EEE m.hotwagner@eee-info.net
Andrea Moser	Public relations officer Responsible for implementation of dissemination and communication activities and networking with other projects and initiatives	EEE a.moser@eee-info.net
Ismini Dimitriadou	Coordinator for technical exchange Responsible for the communication and exchange with the BRIDGE Initiative and similar projects	HYPERTECH i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr
Tamara Hajdu	Living Lab coordinator Responsible for the dissemination and communication activities in the Living Labs	SIN tamara.hajdu@smartinnovationnorway.com

2.2. Target groups and key stakeholders

Key stakeholders of the ACCEPT target audience can be grouped into several categories. Table 2 shows several target groups of the project including several high-level and low-level stakeholders.

Table 2: Updated table of key stakeholders identified as target audience of ACCEPT

Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Energy retailers	Citizens / Building residents	EU institutions (EC, European Science Foundation, MEPs)
Aggregators	Facility managers (e.g. EV charging point operators)	National public authorities (industrial committees, national regulation authorities, ministries and regional councils)
DSOs & TSOs	Commercial Customers	Related EU-funded projects
Distributed Renewable Energy Sources	Residential Customers	Organizations & EU alliances in topics addressed by ACCEPT
ESCOs	Stakeholders at the pilot sites	European technology platforms and respective clusters
Technology providers	General public	Public bodies & environmental organizations
Scientific community	Energy Communities	Regulatory Authorities
Balancing Responsible Parties		
Research community		

This list of key stakeholders is continuously updated as the project progresses and is included in the updated versions of the dissemination and communication plan.

The ACCEPT project will result in high value for end users, as the solutions provided will be adapted to their needs based on a co-creation process through continuous interaction between the consortium and end user representatives, to ensure a high level of user acceptance. However, the dissemination activities target audience will also go beyond end-users as the main potential customers of the ACCEPT solutions are also decision makers (site managers, CEO, board of directors, etc.) and the project scale-up will need facilitators. Special attention will be given to the dissemination of the project results on national level and EU level to reach out to those mentioned stakeholder groups. Since the previous report the consortium identified new key stakeholders for the ACCEPT project, which are balancing responsible parties, research communities, energy communities and regulatory authorities. Based on the activities within the project and the pilot regions the importance of identifying new and/or more specific target groups and stakeholders in terms of their interest of the project and their relevance to maybe influence the success of project goals and enrich the project outcomes.

National level

- National exhibitions related to smart grids, energy storage, energy efficiency, etc.
- Expert conferences and discussions
- Workshops and seminars
- Events in pilot regions

EU level

- European Business Council for Sustainable Energy (e5)
- Union of the Electricity Industry – Eurelectric
- European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy (ECEE)
- European Energy Exchange Associations (e.g., Europex)

To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, within ACCEPT there are two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups will be represented – the user group and the stakeholder ecosystem. In the following sections this approach is described more in detail.

2.2.1. User group

For the User Group (UG) the project aimed to establish a pool of existing and potential participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities. These stakeholders are critical for successful validation and the generation of reliable, trustworthy conclusions. As a result, ACCEPT has established the UG at the project onset according to the citizen engagement methodology to ensure not only adequate participation in demonstration activities, but also that participants co-create the ACCEPT solution and evaluate it as independent beta users that will generate feedback and recommendations. This should help the consortium to identify weaknesses in the user experience and interfaces and lead to improvements for easier market penetration. This shall include both physical and digital engagement means/activities and strive to maintain a constantly open communication channel with the users.

This group can be defined as “pilot level stakeholders” and the definition and engagement are linked to WP2, WP3 and Living Lab activities, as there already have been executed a lot of recruitment activities (WP2/T2.1 Concept Survey, WP6/T6.1 Ex-ante survey, WP3/T3.1 Living Lab activities and collaboration, WP3/T3.4 Stakeholder and community mapping at pilot sites). The identification of the UG within ACCEPT was done in strong collaboration with those partners (WP/Task leaders and pilot partners).

The **objectives** for the **User Group** are:

- **Providing input** based on their knowledge on the energy system, energy pricing, energy communities
- **Feedback** on needs, interest, challenges, desired benefit/outcome in relation to the overall project, as well as offered tools and services
- **Enabling** of an easier implementation and smooth operation of pilot activities
- **Validate** the project outcomes
- **Identify** support needs in the different phase of the project/pilot implementation and execution

The mapping of this “pilot level stakeholders” was done within the frame of Deliverable D3.7 which describes the engagement roadmap for interacting with pilot stakeholders and validating the ACCEPT services design as well as the mapping of stakeholders and planning of the required engagements.

The key stakeholders in each pilot were identified by the pilot representatives. A community stakeholder matrix mapping analysis was undertaken to determine the role each stakeholder has concerning the ACCEPT project, considering also the dimensions of interest and influence. The results are demonstrated within Deliverable 3.7 and how the interaction from project to pilot level occurred and how again the pilot site level stakeholders interacted and involved their stakeholders, is specified in Deliverable D3.3.

2.2.2. Stakeholder ecosystem

The second key group includes market stakeholders who can provide an independent viewpoint and enhance the exploitation potential of project outputs by contributing to their design and creation. For this purpose, ACCEPT has established a “Stakeholder Ecosystem” (SE), to actively involve it in project activities in a consultancy, advisory manner. It includes members that are direct stakeholders in the domains of ACCEPT interest and especially key market verticals, such as demand response, building energy management, flexibility management, retailing, etc.

The SE can be defined as “project level stakeholders” and shall serve the purpose of an Advisory Board with emphasis on market and exploitation aspects, such as:

- Expand the consortium’s viewpoint beyond the mere interest of its members
- Infuse the project with novel ideas regarding new exploitation opportunities and how to address them
- Ensure alignment of project outcomes with the expectations of the market stakeholders
- Enhance the relevance of project outcomes for further national markets in the EU and beyond

The **objectives** for the **Stakeholder Ecosystem** are:

- **Providing input** based on their expertise and field of activity
- **Guidance** on direction and expected outcomes
- **Definition** of success factors and expectation on replicability
- **Promotion** of the project in European networks
- **Feedback** on business models
- **Validation** of project outcomes for a broader impact

Within the ACCEPT project, the communication towards these stakeholder groups took on two complementary approaches. One approach was more formalised, where the official channels of the project were used (e.g., social media campaigns, monthly living labs meetings, etc.) and the other was more informal and conducted on an ad hoc basis (either between WP3 leads and the pilot partners, or between the pilot partners and those members of their community either involved directly with the project or interested in its positive development).

This two-step approach allowed for dynamic, flexible, and iterative communication channels to develop with informal communications often informing the more formal processes within the project.

2.3. Overview of dissemination and communication activities

Within the ACCEPT project, a variety of communication activities will be carried out, using different dissemination means.

- **Raise awareness and engage citizens**
Dissemination activities toward citizens are very specific and critical to the project success and include:

 - promotion of awareness about project goals and activities among the pilot actors
 - fostering the active acceptance for pilot activities impacting the participants
 - establishment and maintenance of adequate communication channels with all types of pilot participants.
- **Project web portal and social media presence**
A very important aspect is to create the project web portal in the first months of the project as well as to establish a representative social media presence in the most popular channels. The project website & social media channels will communicate the objectives, activities and results to the public at large and all partners will have an open attitude and share as much as possible with the public through these channels.
- **Project brochure**
The project brochure will be a key document, to be distributed by the Consortium as a whole and by each Consortium partner, as widely as possible.
- **Participation in fora & thematic events**
To raise project awareness, to present the project results and to liaise with potential stakeholders, it is foreseen to participate in in events like Concertation Meetings, industry and professional initiatives, thematic working groups and “Info Days”. Booths in targeted events in each participating country (i.e., InfoSystem expo, annually in Greece, etc.) shall help the project to engage stakeholders from different industrial domains. Participation in the major events (i.e., ICT, Energy 202x, Smart Grid- Technology and Markets, etc.) will give the chance to present the project to professionals involved in smart grids and to potential buyers. These events attract up to 850,000 visitors every year and open the opportunity to present the projects objectives and mission to European policy-makers, stakeholders and the general public.
- **Liaison with professional communities and networks**
Technological Platforms, Industrial Associations and Initiatives targeting the advancement in Smart Power Electronics, Local Energy Systems/ Microgrids, DR, smart grids, interoperability, energy markets and standardization, are key dissemination/ exploitation fora to be actively utilized by the ACCEPT consortium. Targeted synergies and interactions will be set up, capitalizing the strong links between the consortium partners and such entities. The project will cooperate with EU-funded projects that also focus on the Smart Grids and Demand Response domains, in order to exchange experiences and create synergies.
- **Contributions to regulations and policy-making activities**
Within the ACCEPT project the work of regulatory bodies and relevant data protection recommendations will be monitored to shape the requirements for ACCEPT applications and services. Moreover, ACCEPT aims to actively contribute to ongoing work of regulation bodies, policy makers and expert groups e.g., through partner involvement in the relevant expert groups of the Smart Grid Task Force.
In addition to the above means of dissemination, ACCEPT will also produce and disseminate promotional videos, newsletters, press releases, brochures, posters, slides and leaflets presenting the project concept and achievements.

- **Awareness raising and engagement activities to stimulate key target groups**

To better focus its dissemination effort and improve the effectiveness and reach of dissemination efforts, ACCEPT has created two groups with dedicated needs and objectives, in which the project target groups are represented.

There is the “User Group” (UG) which comprises a pool of participants in the project pilot demonstration and validation activities and the second key group includes market stakeholders (“Stakeholder Ecosystem” (SE)). An appropriate “Stakeholder Ecosystem” was already found that can be actively involved in the project activities.

3. Visual identity

The visual identity of the project begins with the logo, is established through online appearances (website, social media) and regularly consolidated in print material, brochures, flyers, etc.

3.1. Logo

The logo was created by EEE (Figure 5), it illustrates the project acronym (“ACCEPT”) as well as the project title – “active communities & energy prosumers for the energy transition”.

Figure 5: ACCEPT project logo

In the report “D9.1 – ACCEPT branding, website and social media channels” the symbolism of the logo, the background and the intended messages are described.

The art style and the colors of the logo are used in every visual representation of the project to facilitate the establishment of the project branding and to ensure the brand recognition.

3.2. Project presentations

To ensure quick recognition by partners, stakeholders and target audiences, an overall project design was created based on the project logo.

3.2.1. PowerPoint Presentations

A PowerPoint template was created to have a consistent style for all meetings and presentations, which can be edited by the consortium to their specific needs and contexts (see Figure 6). This template is regularly updated and extended, based on needs from the different project partners and also to have all the information about the project partners, logos, etc. up to date (see Figure 6 and Figure 7).

Figure 6: ACCEPT presentation template slides.

In addition, a general project presentation was created in order to communicate the general project information in a uniform way:

Figure 7: ACCEPT general project presentation slides.

3.3. Project Leaflet

To share the ideas and goals of the project with as many stakeholders as possible, the ACCEPT general project leaflet was created. The main focus for this trifold-leaflet was to create it in a simple language for all stakeholder groups to understand and not go too much into technical detail and lose their interest.

The leaflet contains:

- A front page including:
 - the project logo
 - the project slogan “a digital toolbox for energy communities”
 - project website & social media channels links
- The inside, containing:
 - the list of all participating partners by country
 - a map to present all participating countries as well as the locations of the 4 Living Labs
 - general information about the Living Labs
 - short descriptions of the 4 Living Labs
- The project information page with
 - project timeline & key facts
 - project introduction
- A backside including:
 - the logos of all project partners
 - the project’s social media channels and website links
 - contact information of the project coordinator and the dissemination team
 - the EU emblem (see 3.4)
 - a disclaimer

The general project leaflet is visible in the following Figure 8:

Figure 8: ACCEPT general project leaflet.

3.1. Project Poster / Roll-Ups

3.1.1. Project Poster

Figure 9: ACCEPT project poster.

3.1.2. Project Roll-Ups

For dissemination purposes up to now two project Roll-Ups have been created. The first project Roll-Up was produced at the beginning of the project and updated during the previous months and in addition a second project Roll-Up was created to show more details on booths on events, conferences, etc.

The first project Roll-Up is focused on:

- General project focus
- General project information (duration, partners, partner countries, Living Labs, etc.)

The second Roll-Up contains deeper information on project goals and objectives (see Figure 10 and Figure 11).

Figure 10: ACCEPT project Roll-Up Nr. 1

Figure 11: ACCEPT project Roll-Up Nr. 2

3.1.1. Project Video

As additional and important dissemination material a project video was created as it was seen as an effective way to showcase the objectives, activities, achievements, etc. of the ACCEPT project and share it with a wider audience. For the creation of an engaging and informative video different steps have been conducted.

In a first step the purpose of the video was defined, as well as the target audience and how the content and results of the project shall be presented in order to structure the video effectively. Then the content was planned, by outlining the key messages and information that the ACCEPT project wishes to convey in the video. Then they have been broken down into sections to ensure a logical flow. Templates have been created and circulated in order to gather input material from technical project partners, pilot leaders, etc. Based on this the script for the video was created as well as the necessary visual assets. Figure 12 shows the publication of the ACCEPT project video on the projects' website.

Figure 12: ACCEPT project Video on the projects' website <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

Figure 13: ACCEPT project Video on YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r1JUjVx5ciU>

3.1.2. Project info-campaign

For dissemination purposes it was also seen as an important aspect to create an information campaign to raise additional awareness, improve engagement towards the target audience, and promote the project's goals. For the planning and creation of the info-campaign the following steps have been conducted:

1. *Define campaign objectives:* In a first step it was identified what the project intends to achieve with the information campaign. This was important to guide your campaign's direction.
2. *Identify target audience:* In a next step the target audience was determined, who the campaign is intended to reach. This was important to tailor the messaging and communication channels effectively.

3. *Key messages:* Then the development of concise and compelling messages that convey the essence of the project was done. Focus on the benefits, impact, and value the project brings. The creation of clear and easy to understand messages was important.
4. *Selection of dissemination channels:* It was also important to identify the most appropriate channels to reach the target audience. In this context mainly online platforms have been selected to be the main dissemination channels for the info-campaign.
5. *Develop content:* After this process, the most important step was to create and structure the content for the video, that support the key messages and engage the audience. It was important to ensure that the content is informative, visually appealing, and shareable to maximize its reach.

The following topics have been defined for the info-campaign and appropriate information has been created:

- Relationship to the European Green Deal
- Citizen engagement & energy communities
- Digital toolbox and digital services
- Overview of the 4 living labs
- Consumer engagement: Method
- Consumer engagement: Living labs
- Consumer engagement: drivers and factors for development
- Citizen Digital Twin: Home automation
- Citizen App: Smart Living
- Citizen App: Community engagement
- Energy Community Tools: general
- ECT platform: Horizontal Tools
- ECT platform: Vertical Tools
- Energy Community services I
- Energy Community as an Energy Service Company
- Energy Community as a retailer
- Energy Community as an Aggregator
- Pilot/Living Lab Netherlands
- Pilot/Living Lab Spain
- Pilot/Living Lab Greece
- Pilot/Living Lab Switzerland

6. *Establish a content calendar:* Then a content distribution schedule was planned and organized. This content plan helps to stay consistent and ensure a steady flow of information throughout the campaign. The frequency of posts and optimal times for engagement has been defined.
7. *Start info-campaign:* Finally, the info-campaign was started and published on the projects' social media channels. In addition, a new menu at the website was created named "encyclopedia" sharing all the content of the info-campaign.

Some examples of the visual material that was created based on the different topics of the info-campaign, can be seen in Figure 14.

Figure 14: ACCEPT project info-campaign excerpt.

3.2. Acknowledging the EU funding

Any communication activity related to the H2020 ACCEPT project needs to acknowledge the EU funding received, according to the grant agreement signed. This means that the EU emblem needs to be displayed with every communication action as well as the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.” In practice, it looks like this:

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 957781.

What’s more, when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

4. Homepage

By the end of M3, the official project website was launched. It serves the purpose to not only inform and engage the public about the project and present a chance to contact the project’s reference persons, but also connect the consortium through different forms, a common repository for document sharing and mailing lists.

The official ACCEPT project website can be reached at www.accept-project.eu

Figure 15: ACCEPT website main page (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

The structure of the ACCEPT project website is as follows:

Figure 8: ACCEPT website structure

4.1. Website Content

4.1.1. Project news

The project news part is placed on the main page of the project website. Current activities in the project and other project-relevant news are published there.

Figure 16: News section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/project-news>)

4.1.2. Events

The events part is also placed on the main page of the project website. Project events and other project-relevant international events are published there.

Figure 17: Events section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

4.1.3. About the project

In the tab "About the project" the introduction of the project is included with the main goals, the ACCEPT approach and tools, including technical and technological objectives, as well as objectives on citizen engagement and co-creation activities. In this section also the Work packages are described.

Figure 18: "About the project" section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/about>)

4.1.4. Consortium

Project partner logos with respective subpages with information about the PPs, which was obtained in advance from the PPs are included in this section of the website.

Figure 19: Consortium section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/consortium>)

4.1.5. Living labs

Description of the living labs and location of the pilot sites is demonstrated in this section.

Figure 20: Living Lab section of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/living-labs>)

4.1.6. Library

Public Dissemination material and media, Newsletters, Public Deliverables, Scientific Papers can be seen and accessed within this section.

Figure 21: Project Library of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/library>)

4.1.7. Legal Notice, Privacy Policy, Footer

At the bottom of each page at the website there are also the buttons to access the legal notice and privacy policy of the project. In addition, the footer of the websites includes:

- Social media links
- Newsletter registration form
- Twitter feed
- Contact information
- EU emblem and project disclaimer
- Bridge link

Figure 22: Footer of the ACCEPT website (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

4.1.1. Encyclopedia

As a new and informative part within the ACCEPT project website a part called "Encyclopedia" was added, which should serve as valuable resource for knowledge sharing by the project. The first important content in the Encyclopedia was sharing the info-campaign.

Figure 23: ACCEPT Encyclopedia (<https://www.accept-project.eu/>)

5. Social media

The social media channels will be the backbone of the dissemination and communication activities. Short pieces of information, easy to digest for the reader, presented with illustrations or graphical elements will be issued in a continuous way. Through this, the key messages of the project can be shared with the target audiences. Revision and repetition are in this sense crucial, since the project itself is quite technical and complex topics are addressed.

What's more, social media channels open up the possibility of a dialogue with certain target audiences, networking and exchange with professional initiatives, experts, platforms and organizations. To this end, these channels will be an important platform for establishing exploitation options and cooperation in the later stages of the project.

In M1 of the project, the following social media channels have been established:

Twitter – AcceptH2020
<https://twitter.com/AcceptH2020>

LinkedIn – Accept_H2020
www.linkedin.com/company/Accept-H2020

YouTube – Accept_H2020
https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCsFhR-shQ8e_nkhqo5D4vVA

Figure 10: ACCEPT Twitter profile

Figure 11: ACCEPT LinkedIn business profile

Figure 12: ACCEPT Youtube channel

5.1. Social Media activity plan

In order to avoid having a one-sided communication and to provide a holistic view of the project and project partners activities, each partner is asked to provide input for our social media channels. This ensures a constant social media activity and a reporting of all aspects of the ACCEPT project.

According to the plan to have at least one posting on the Social Media accounts, in the initial plan there have been two project partners assigned to provide some sort of input. After the evaluation of the performance of the Social Media activities, the Social Media plans have been adopted with just one partner to provide input per week and additionally also technical partners, Task Leaders, Pilot Partners are always asked to provide input as soon as there is any news out of their activities. Input to our social media isn't limited to concrete project activities, but also various other input, for example:

- A link to a relevant (online) article / news item
- A posting of some related activity within the organization (related publications, participation at some event, results from other related projects, etc.)
- A link to a video related to the project or your current activities

These scheduled social media activities are the foundation of our online communication. The partners are reminded at the beginning of each month that it's their turn to provide a Social Media article. On the schedule they can see the week that is assigned to them for providing in input to the project's online channels. In the first months of the project kind of periodic Social Media Activity Plans have been produced and provided (see Figure 24), but to have it shorter term and to be able to address some specific partners instead of the overall consortium, monthly social media plans have been created (see Figure 24)

Figure 24: ACCEPT Monthly Social Media activity plan example October 2022 and February 2023.

6. Newsletter

In addition to other communication channels a bi-annual issue of electronic newsletters will help to further educate the project’s target groups, stakeholders and end-users on a regular basis. Other than in social media for example, newsletters leave space to address certain aspects and milestones of the project more in detail.

EEE as dissemination and communication leader will regularly prepare the structure and basic content of the newsletter issues. All partners will contribute if required to highlight certain aspects of their work, reports, intermediate results or pilot site experiences. Content-wise the newsletters be oriented towards the communication-timeline outlined in 2.1.3. In the initial phase of the project awareness raising and information provision will be a central part of the messages to be delivered through this channel. As the project progresses hands-on experiences from the pilot sites as well as technical developments and other project results will come more into focus.

Events and other communication channels (e.g., social media, homepage) will be used to gain subscribers, but also all project partners commit to reach out to their already established networks (on national/regional or international level) to get subscribers for electronic newsletters.

The newsletters are created using a web-based email marketing service. The distribution is carried out through a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the project’s website.

Figure 14: Sign-up form for newsletters on the ACCEPT website

According to the plan it is foreseen to produce semestral issues of the ACCEPT Newsletter and send it to all receivers who opted-in via the ACCEPT website.

The first issue of the newsletter can be accessed under the following link:

<https://mailchi.mp/76975d516c07/accept-newsletter-1>

The second issue of the newsletter can be accessed here:

<https://mailchi.mp/8a7967d74371/accept-newsletter-2>

The third issue of the newsletter can be accessed here.

<https://mailchi.mp/f634b30233a0/accept-newsletter-3>

The fourth issue of the newsletter can be accessed here:

<https://mailchi.mp/6ae7ccb706a7/accept-newsletter-4>

Also the fifth version of the newsletter was created within the respective period.

D9.4 – ACCEPT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN AND ACTIVITY REPORT V3

ACCEPT Newsletter #1

This is the first issue of the Newsletter of the H2020 project ACCEPT. You received this newsletter because you subscribed to our mailing list on the project's website. In this issue we will introduce to you the project itself, its scope and objectives, and we will give you an update of the project activities so far.

Thank you very much for signing up!

About the project

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 project ACCEPT intends to develop and deliver a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated in four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3000 people and 750 residences.

The Consortium

ACCEPT Newsletter #2

This is the second issue of the Newsletter of the H2020 project ACCEPT.

You received this newsletter because you subscribed to our mailing list on the project's website. In this issue we will give you an insight into our living labs and update you about the project activities.

Thank you very much for signing up!

About the project

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 project ACCEPT intends to develop and deliver a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated in four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3000 people and 750 residences.

Living Lab Update

The Arena Innovation Community (AIC) in Switzerland will be operational in the first months of 2022, when all required installations are completed. Among others, installation and commissioning of the 60kWh/60kW district battery, which began in late 2021, is expected to be completed by mid-January. The battery system represents an essential element of the energy community, helping to increase self-consumption of locally-produced renewable energy up to 90%.

ACCEPT Newsletter #3

This is the third issue of the Newsletter of the H2020 project ACCEPT.

You received this newsletter because you subscribed to our mailing list on the project's website. In this issue we will give you an insight into our living labs and update you about the project activities.

Thank you very much for signing up!

About the project

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 project ACCEPT intends to develop and deliver a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated at four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3,000 people and 750 residences.

After 10 months in the project, it is now time to get a better view on the project's bigger picture. In this issue of the ACCEPT newsletter, we would like to give you an overview of the activities performed over the past six months within the ACCEPT project.

ACCEPT Technical Solutions

The preliminary version of the ACCEPT toolbox is already developed. It allows the optimisation of the operation of appliances at participants' households for achieving best energy and/or energy efficiency, depending on desired revenue streams, etc. The operation of the household appliances is optimised in such a way which ensures that the comfort and convenience of the participants is not jeopardised (i.e. maintained).

The ACCEPT toolbox, besides offering benefits for the end customers, offers benefits for the electricity network as well. It helps the network increase level of the demand in the active duration of high renewable generation or high demand through the engagement of consumers and prosumers in schemes promoting the increased consumption of self-generated energy, energy efficiency, etc.

The back-end systems of the ACCEPT toolbox are currently installed at the laboratory facilities of involved partners and will also be rolled out at the participants' households.

There are also two front-end systems for the end user, but also the project partners working on the issue at the four different pilot locations. The first one is related to the Citizen App, which the support of the Energy Community Platform.

CITIZEN APP

A first preliminary version of the Citizen App is ready. Through this component the end users will be able to interact with the ACCEPT solution and the appliances in their households. For example, end-users will be able to monitor any device within their premises and provide their availability for any upcoming Demand Response events.

ACCEPT Newsletter #4

This is the fourth issue of the Newsletter of the H2020 project ACCEPT.

You received this newsletter because you subscribed to our mailing list on the project's website. In this issue we will give you an insight into our living labs and update you about the project activities.

Thank you very much for signing up!

About the project

The EU-funded Horizon 2020 project ACCEPT intends to develop and deliver a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated at four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3,000 people and 750 residences.

After 2 years in the project, it is now time to get a better view on the project's bigger picture. In this issue of the ACCEPT newsletter, we would like to give you an overview of the activities performed over the past six months within the ACCEPT project.

Status of ACCEPT's technical solutions

The preliminary version of the digital toolbox developed in ACCEPT for helping energy communities and their members play a more active role in the energy transition is now available!

The Citizen Application, the mobile app which allows citizens to monitor their energy consumption and control remotely their appliances, has been released to selected users for monitoring feedback. A questionnaire was shared with these citizens for assessing the performance of the application in a more representative manner, also allowing the incorporation of responses coming from the different energy communities.

The Energy Community Platform, which allows the energy community members to visualize key energy related information of their communities (such as the available flexibility that their community can offer to other parties, e.g., their local grid operators), has been demonstrated as part of a dedicated workshop. The feedback received by the community is currently being implemented before the release of the next version of the platform in December.

The ACCEPT back-end system, the engine working behind the scenes (i.e., the applications mentioned above) in optimizing energy consumption and offering necessary actions for revenue generation to community members, are currently being expanded and enhanced with new features. As more the available and increasing data in the project, allowing us to combine useful data and information from users, the back-end systems become more accurate and we are getting a step closer to the final ACCEPT solution, which we anticipate being ready in the first quarter of 2023.

Figure 14: ACCEPT Newsletters

7. Scientific publications

Dissemination activities concentrate on the diffusion of scientific and technological knowledge, generated within the context of the project, to large groups of relevant stakeholders, both academic and market actors. The aim is to ensure the long-term impact of ACCEPT, in terms of communicating, but also exploiting, the project's results.

To that extent, the dissemination objectives extend beyond activities related to the technical work in ACCEPT, towards reaching out to larger audiences that are active in the relevant fields of research and innovation.

As mentioned in the ACCEPT Description of Work (DoW), this dissemination goal will be achieved primarily by means of publishing scientific articles in journals and organizing/participating in conferences, panels, workshops, roundtables relevant to the project's research and innovation activities. In this way, we will be able to reinforce the project image and brand, cross-fertilize ACCEPT concepts and solutions with state-of-the-art techniques, foster cross-project cooperation and provide a fundamental verification of soundness of project results via peer review.

The action plan to be adopted consists of three distinct steps that are to be repeated in a 6-monthly (in the case of conferences/other events) or yearly basis (in the case of journals):

1. Identification of relevant scientific journals and/or events by the relevant project partners (project coordinator, project dissemination manager, research organizations)
2. Round table between partners for generating a time plan with articles to be published/events to be attended or organized.
3. Implementation of the time plan by the consortium.

Within the ACCEPT project the following scientific publication have been created and published:

Table 3: List of Scientific publications.

Publication title	Project Partner	Type of publication	Date	Link
Enabling Technologies for Wide-Scale Implementation of Energy Communities' Projects	Hypertech	Proceedings	25.11.2021	https://www.mdpi.com/2673-4931/11/1/14 https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2021011014
Interoperability of Flexibility Assets v2.0	Hypertech	Scientific publication / White paper	01.05.2022	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/a00be176-ac1f-11ed-b508-01aa75ed71a1/language-en
Operationalising participation: Key obstacles and drivers to Citizen Energy Community formation in Europe's Energy Transition	UCC	Conference paper	20.06.2022	https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/international-conference-on-energy-research-and-social-science
Effect of sustainable Local Energy Communities on LV distribution networks	CIRCE	Scientific publication	28-30.11.2022	http://2022.icsc-cities.com/index.html
Smart Built4EU, Task Force 3, Topic C: Data driven indicators for smart buildings	Hypertech	White Paper	11.01.2023	https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/publications/
Operationalizing participation: Key obstacles and drivers to citizen energy community formation in Europe's energy transition	UCC	Journal article	01.03.2023	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sctalk.2022.100104
Initial Assessment of Electrical Flexibility of Combustion-Based District Heating Systems	CIRCE	Scientific publication	06-09.06.2023	https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14095.87200

7.1. Relevant Scientific Journals

7.1.1. Classic Scientific Journals

In the following the most relevant academic and scientific journals for the publications in ACCEPT are listed. Publications in ACCEPT will not only, but preferably, address these journals.

- **IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid**
<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-smart-grid>
 The journal publishes original research on theories and principles of smart grid technologies and systems, used in demand response, Advance Metering Infrastructure, cyber-physical systems, multi-energy systems, transactive energy, data analytics, and EV integration.
- **IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy**
<https://www.ieee-pes.org/publications/transactions/transactions-on-sustainable-energy>
 The journal publishes original research on design, implementation, grid-integration and control of sustainable energy technologies and systems.
- **Elsevier – Applied Energy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/applied-energy>
 It provides a forum for information on innovation, research, development and demonstration in the areas of energy conversion and conservation, the optimal use of energy resources, analysis and optimization of energy processes, mitigation of environmental pollutants, and sustainable energy systems.
- **Elsevier – Journal of Cleaner Production**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-cleaner-production>
 An international, transdisciplinary journal focusing on Cleaner Production, Environmental, and Sustainability research and practice. Subject areas include, but are not limited to: Cleaner production and technical processes, Sustainable Development and Sustainability, Sustainable Consumption, Environmental and sustainability assessment, Sustainable Products and Services, Corporate sustainability and Corporate Social Responsibility, Education for Sustainable Development, Governance, legislation, and policy for sustainability
- **Elsevier – Energy and Buildings**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-and-buildings>
 An international journal publishing articles with explicit links to energy use in buildings.
- **Elsevier - Energy Research & Social Science**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-research-and-social-science/>
 Publishes research examining the relationship between energy systems and society.
- **Elsevier - Energy Policy**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-policy>
 International peer-reviewed journal addressing the policy implications of energy supply and use from their economic, social, planning and environmental aspects.
- **MDPI – Energies**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/energies>
 Energies is a peer-reviewed, open access journal of related scientific research, technology development, engineering, and the studies in policy and management and is published semimonthly online by MDPI. The journal covers research in energy engineering and sciences, with a strong focus on energy storage and conservation, biomass and bioenergy, renewable energy, electricity supply and demand, energy in buildings, and on economic and policy issues. The journal also welcomes papers on related topics such as energy modelling and prediction, integrated energy systems, energy planning and management, provided such topics are within the context of the broader multi-disciplinary scope of energy.
- **MDPI – Electricity**
<https://www.mdpi.com/journal/electricity>
 Electricity is an international peer-reviewed open access journal on electrical engineering published quarterly online by MDPI. The scope of Electricity includes: Electric Power Systems, Energy Conversion, Power Markets

and Economics, Smart Grids and Smart Electricity Applications, Electricity Storage, Electric Transportation, Electric Infrastructure and Applications, Environmental Issues and Electric Engineering Education.

- **SAGE - Energy and Environment**

<https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/energy-environment/journal202462#ManuscriptPrep>

Interdisciplinary journal that encourages dialogue between the social sciences as energy demand and supply are observed and analyzed with reference to politics of policy-making and its implementation.

- **Wiley - International Journal of Energy Research**

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1099114x>

Focus on energy management, production, conversion, conservation, systems, technologies and applications, and their impact on the environment and sustainable development.

- **Springer - Energy, Sustainability and Society**

<https://energysustainsoc.biomedcentral.com>

Forum for research, development & implementation of sustainable energy systems.

7.1.2. Hybrid Scientific Journals (research, but also for professional communities)

- **Elsevier - Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews**
<https://www.journals.elsevier.com/renewable-and-sustainable-energy-reviews>
 Focuses on renewable and sustainable energy in order to bring together the research community, the private sector and policy and decision makers.
- **Science Direct - Renewable Energy**
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-energy>
 Renewable Energy seeks to promote and disseminate knowledge on the various topics and technologies of renewable energy systems and components. The journal aims to serve researchers, engineers, economists, manufacturers, NGOs, associations and societies to help them keep abreast of new developments in their specialist fields and to apply alternative energy solutions to current practices.

7.2. Relevant Scientific Conferences and Workshops

7.2.1. Conferences

To raise awareness about the project, to exchange knowledge, to disseminate project findings, learnings and key outputs, the participation to conferences is seen as an important C&D activity. Consortium members are requested to look for and inform the consortium about suitable conferences for active participation.

In the following a non-exhaustive list of annual conferences is given:

- Energy Research & Social Science Conference
- BEHAVE European Conference on Behaviour and Energy Efficiency
- ICESS International Conference on Energy, Society and Sustainability
- World Sustainable Energy Days
- RGS-IBG Annual International Conference
- EEEIC – International Conference on Environmental and Electrical Engineering
- UPEC - International Universities Power Engineering Conference
- IEEE ISGT Europe conference
- PowerTech conference
- Enlit Europe

7.2.1. Past conferences

The events where the ACCEPT project partners are participating are documented in the Dissemination and Communication monitoring tool of each partner and reported to the Dissemination and communication coordinator after request. The most relevant visibility of ACCEPT in different conferences was (Table 4):

Table 4: Participation of ACCEPT partners in conferences

Conference Name	Date(s)	Comment
ICSC-CITIES 2022 (V Congreso Ibero-Americano de Ciudades Inteligentes)	28-30.11.2022	CIRCE participated to this event http://2022.icsc-cities.com/index.html
2023 IEEE EEEIC23 + I&CPS Europe	06-09.06.2023	CIRCE participated to this event https://www.eeeic.net/eeeic/
InnoGrid 2022	14.06.2022	Hypertech participated online to the event, value for Customers delivered by the ACCEPT project https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InEEIWdKOA&ab_channel=ENTSO-E-EuropeanNetworkofTransmissionSystemOperatorsforElectricity

7.2.2. Workshops

To increase the outreach of the ACCEPT project and mainly to exchange knowledge and experiences, it is an important aspect to organize and participate to workshops and webinars. As for all the other external events and conferences, ACCEPT project partners are requested to look for relevant workshops and webinars, to inform the consortium and to initiate discussions on the participation of suitable project partners.

Besides the mentioned workshops related to the creation of synergies with other EU projects (described in chapter 10 of this Deliverable) and the workshops within BRIDGE (described in chapter 9 of this Deliverable), the following participation to workshops/webinars was conducted by ACCEPT project partners (Table 5):

Table 5: Participation of ACCEPT project partners in workshops

Name	Date	Link
Sustainable Places 2022 / Fostering User Engagement for Innovative Demand Response For Effective Flexibility (collaborative workshop with sister projects)	08.09.2022	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dTVsj4BGaZ0&ab_channel=SustainablePlaces
Sustainable Places 2023 / Innovative solution and co-creation for effective implementation of demand response (collaborative workshop with sister projects)	14.06.2023	-

Dissemination and communication activities of special importance are also the training and stakeholder engagement activities within the pilot regions. These activities are subsumed under the framework of the “Living Lab Workshops”, comprising training sessions for the Living Lab participants as well as feedback sessions for a wider audience. The detailed Living Lab activities are carried out within the frame of WP3 and will especially be supported by WP9.

Within WP3 the following engagement activities, workshops, etc. with both stakeholder groups have been conducted:

- Capacity building workshop
- Pilot site visits
- User testing of the citizen app
- Persona development

Details are summarized in Deliverable D3.3 – Living Lab activities plan and evaluation report v3.

7.3. Open Access Repositories

In Deliverable D9.2 – ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication Plan and Activity report v1 a list of different open access repositories was provided and based on the decision of the project consortium “Zenodo” was selected.

In D1.3 the second version of the Data Management Plan it was identified that Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts.

As also stated in D1.3 it is a primary requirement from the European Commission guidelines on data management to make research data 'FAIR', meaning that they are findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. In detail there are four driving principles declared for ensuring that data are findable.

- (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

By adopting Zenodo as the project’s data repository, it is possible to cover all of the above, based on its provided functionality. In particular:

- a DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo
- Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments
- the DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record
- metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

Each of the above bullets satisfies the respective requirement presented in the first list of this subsection. Descriptive metadata will include (but not be limited to): authors, subject, domain, high-level description/abstract, date of generation/publication, project information, manual. The consortium will strive to use open formats whenever possible for all documentation and data.

For the ACCEPT project, all public and approved Deliverables have been uploaded to the Zenodo repository and can be found under the following link <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=H2020%20ACCEPT>. Figure 25 shows an excerpt of the list of Deliverables that are uploaded to Zenodo:

Figure 25: Deliverables uploaded to Zenodo.

8. Media

There are various communication channels, which can be subsumed in this category. These channels can differ very much in their character regarding aspects like range, however, one aspect remains the same with respect to the project’s approach to the utilization of them: media channels will be utilized throughout the project in an “ad hoc”-way.

Dissemination in magazines, blogs, TV or even through print media via press releases won’t be strictly scheduled, but utilized in an on-demand way. Taking developments, milestones and especially deployment actions in the pilot sites into account, appropriate media channels will be chosen for specific dissemination actions. Having said that, even within the broad range of media-related communication channels some activities will be carried out on a more regular basis, other actions (like TV contributions) will be primarily based on current developments in the project, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 26: regularity of dissemination activities in media channels.

Following communication in different media channels (press release, contributions on radio/tv, etc.) in the reported project period of this Deliverable can be reported as follows:

Table 6: Communication activities on different media channels M19 - M30

Communication on Channel	Input	Visibility	Date
Social media	Post on twitter: ponencia sobre comunidades de energía	Link	08.07.2022
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	You Tube video: ponencia de La Solar sobre comunidades de energía	Link	08.07.2022
Social media	Post on linkedin: ponencia de la solar sobre comunidades de energía	Link	08.07.2022
Social media	Facebook link:Impulsar el #autoconsumo #fotovoltaico bien de forma individual o colectiva sólo trae ventajas	Link	13.07.2022
Social media	Post on linkedin: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en 7 TV Región de Murcia hablando sobre las comunidades de energía	Link	18.07.2022
Social media	Post on twitter: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en	Link	18.07.2022
Social media	Post on facebook: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en La 7 hablando sobre las comunidades de energía	Link	18.07.2022
Social media	Post on facebook: Financiado con fondos europeos, el proyecto #AcceptH2020 pretende desarrollar y ofrecer un conjunto de herramientas para que las comunidades energéticas ofrezcan servicios innovadores	Link	19.07.2022
Social media	Post on Instagram: Financiado con fondos europeos, el proyecto #AcceptH2020 pretende desarrollar y ofrecer un conjunto de herramientas para que las comunidades energéticas ofrezcan servicios innovadores	Link	19.07.2022
Social Media	Post on sustainability projects - Twitter	Link	20.07.2022
Social Media	Post on sustainability projects - LinkedIn	Link	20.07.2022

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Social media	Francisco Espín, miembro del consejo rector de nuestra cooperativa y director de Efficiency Services Consulting presentó el proyecto "Comunidades Energéticas de la Región de Murcia" en la Federación de Municipios como parte del Proyecto #AcceptH2020	Link	28.07.2022
Social media	Linkedin post: Ponencia sobre comunidades de energía	Link	29.07.2022
Social media	Twitter post: Ponencia sobre comunidsdes de energía	Link	29.07.2022
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	You Tube video: pòncia de La Solar sobre comunidades de energía	Link	29.07.2022
Social media	Post on facebook: ponencia cambio climático	Link	29.07.2022
Social media	Facebook post: Las solar en efficiency consulting	Link	07.08.2022
Social media	Linkedin post:La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético.	Link	09.08.2022
Social media	Twitter: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético.	Link	09.08.2022
Social media	Post on facebook: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético	Link	09.08.2022
Social media	post on instagan: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético	Link	09.08.2022
Social media	Post on facenook: Francisco Espin Sánchez, Director de proyectos de comunidades energéticas concede una entrevista a la #RevistaTécnicaIndustrial,	Link	12.08.2022
Social media	Linkedin post:Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Link	30.08.2022
Social media	Twitter post:Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Link	30.08.2022
Social media	Instagram post: Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos,	Link	30.08.2022
Social media	Facebook post: Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Link	30.08.2022
Social Media	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - Facebook	Link	07.09.2022
Social Media	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - twitter	Link	07.09.2022
Social Media	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - LinkedIn	Link	07.09.2022
Social media	Post On Facebook: Creemos en un planeta descarbonizado y en el que todos podamos ser autosuficientes energéticamente	Link	27.09.2022
Social media	Instagram post: Creemos en un planeta descarbonizado y en el que todos podamos ser autosuficientes energéticamente	Link	27.09.2022
Social Media	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Link	05.10.2022
Social Media	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Link	05.10.2022
Social Media	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Link	05.10.2022
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Website news on the energy saving strategies	Link	06.10.2022
Social media	Post on Facebook: Living Labs	Link	07.10.2022
Social media	Post on Facebook: Living Labs	Link	07.10.2022
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Webiste news on research and development activities of AEM	Link	09.10.2022
Social media	Post on Instagram: Programa CE Implementa	Link	21.10.2022
Social media	Post on Facebook: Programa CE Implementa para comunidades energéticas	Link	21.10.2022
Social media	Linkedin post: Programa CE Implementa para comunidades energéticas.	Link	21.10.2022
Social media	Instagram post: @mejor_conectados	Link	04.11.2022
Social media	Post on Facebook: Mejor Conectados	Link	04.11.2022

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Social media	Linkedin post: Mejor Conectados	Link	04.11.2022
Social media	Twitter Post:	Link	04.11.2022
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Website news on the advantages of energy communities	Link	08.11.2022
Social media	Post on instagram: Lideramos el proyecto #accepth2020	Link	26.11.2022
Social media	Post on facebook: Lideramos el proyecto #accepth2020	Link	26.11.2022
Social media	linkedin post: Lideramos el proyecto Accept_H2020	Link	26.11.2022
Social media	twitter post: Lideramos el proyecto @AcceptH2020	Link	26.11.2022
Social Media	Post on Enlit event	Link	29.11.2022
Social Media	Post on Enlit event	Link	29.11.2022
Social media	Instagram Post: El Realengo	Link	16.12.2022
Social media	post on facebook: El Realengo	Link	16.12.2022
Social media	linkedin post: El Realengo	Link	16.12.2022
Social media	twitter post: El Realengo	Link	16.12.2022
Communication Campaign (Radio, TV, etc.)	Comunidad energética renovable Bullas: haciendo frente a la pobreza energética	Link	28.12.2022
Social media	Post on Facebook: Mejor Conectados	Link	28.12.2022
Social media	Instagram post: @mejor_conectados	Link	28.12.2022
Social media	Linkedin post: Mejor Conectados	Link	28.12.2022
Social media	Twitter Post: Mejor Conectados	Link	28.12.2022
Social Media	Post on 4th newsletter Facebook	Link	10.01.2023
Social Media	Post on 4th newsletter twitter	Link	10.01.2023
Social Media	Post on Twitter about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Link	17.01.2023
Social Media	Post on LinkedIn about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Link	17.01.2023
Social Media	Post on Facebook about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Link	17.01.2023
Social Media	Post on 4th newsletter linkedin	Link	10.01.2023
Social media	Instagram post: Comunidades energéticas	Link	18.01.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Comunicades energéticas	Link	18.01.2023
Social media	Linkedin Post: Comunidades energéticas	Link	19.01.2023
Social media	Twitter post: Comunidades energéticas	Link	19.01.2023
Social media	Instagram post: Asamblea General	Link	20.01.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Asamblea General	Link	20.01.2023
Social media	Linkedin Post: Asamblea General	Link	20.01.2023
Social media	Twitter post: Asamblea General	Link	20.01.2023
Social Media	LinkedIn post	Link	23.01.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Ecomur	Link	27.01.2023
Social media	Linkedin post: Ecomur	Link	27.01.2023
Social media	Twitter post: Ecomur	Link	27.01.2023
Social media	Instagram post: Diputación de Soria	Link	01.02.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Diputación de Soria	Link	01.02.2023
Social media	Linkedin post: Diputación de Soria	Link	01.02.2023

Social media	Twitter post: Diputación de Soria	Link	01.02.2023
Social Media	Repost on Twitter on complimentary reports into current barriers facing CECs	Link	04.02.2022
Social Media	Post on Facebook about last meeting	Link	02.02.2023
Social Media	Post on Twitter about last meeting	Link	02.02.2023
Social Media	Post on LinkedIn about lasr meeting	Link	02.02.2023
Social Media	Repost on Twitter	Link	14.02.2023
Social Media	Repost on LinkedIn	Link	14.02.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Prueba piloto	Link	08.03.2023
Social media	Instagram Post: Prueba Piloto	Link	08.03.2023
Social media	Twitter Post: Prueba piloto	Link	08.03.2023
Social media	Linkedin Post: Prueba Piloto	Link	08.03.2023
Event	I Fair of Construction and Installation of Solar Power Plants	Link	15.03.2023
Press release	Press Release on local newspaper	Link	19.03.2023
Social Media	Post on twitter about the last event	Link	20.03.2023
Social Media	Post on linkedin about the last event	Link	20.03.2023
Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	The EU Projects Zone Podcast / Presentation of the project	Link	23.03.2023
Social media	Post on Facebook: Hogares Autoconsumo	Link	18.04.2023
Social Media	Repost on Twitter on the Citizen-Application developed by CERTH	Link	09.05.2022

9. Events & Networking

9.1. External events

An effective means for the dissemination of project findings, learnings and key outputs are external events (national and international), such as conferences, fora, panel discussions, summits, symposiums etc. Members of the ACCEPT project should look for and inform the consortium of suitable external events where the project can be represented to increase its visibility. They should also explore opportunities for actively participating in such events to raise awareness on the project and connect with possible key industry stakeholders.

In the following a non-exhaustive list of annual events is given:

- CIREN International conference on electricity distribution, <http://www.cired.net/>
- Enlit Europe, <https://www.enlit-europe.com/euw>
- EUSEW - EU Sustainable Energy Week, <https://www.eusew.eu/>
- InnoGrid <https://www.innogrid.eu/>
- SP - Sustainable Places, <https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/>

For a good and effective project dissemination the goal is to have at least 30 participations to external events within the project lifetime. This goal will be revisited throughout the project and adjusted, if necessary, especially in cases where participation to external events is hindered by externalities, such as the persistent pandemic crisis.

In the Dissemination and Communication Plan the following guidelines for participating in external events have been set:

Before participating in an external event:

If a partner wishes to participate in an external event representing the ACCEPT project, they should let the Project Coordinator and the Dissemination and communication coordinator know in advance, providing them with key information on the event, such as:

- the type and title of the event,
- the event dates,
- the level and nature of participation of the partner at the event (e.g., presentation, panel discussion),
- the event program (if available),
- an estimation of the event attendance costs, etc.

This will allow, on the one hand, to keep track of all project-related dissemination activities and optimally manage the dissemination resources of the project, and on the other hand, to provide the relevant partner with guidance and project dissemination material (if required and where available).

After participating in an external event:

After participating in an external event, and within the first month following the event, relevant partners should update the Dissemination and communication coordinator on the key outcomes/outputs from their participation at the event. Any dissemination material (such as fliers, presentations, etc.) prepared and shared with external stakeholders during the external event, as well as any available event proceedings, should be included in the communication to the Dissemination and communication coordinator. The Dissemination and communication coordinator should then update accordingly the wider consortium and upload all event-related material on the project repository in a folder indicating the event name and dates.

It is strongly recommended that, every time partners actively participate in external events, a specific communication piece is prepared and shared with the wider ACCEPT consortium, as well as publicly via social media (including on the project’s own social media pages) and the websites of the project and ACCEPT partners.

Finally, a list of all past external events attended was created and will be maintained and regularly updated by the Dissemination and communication coordinator. This list is included in the upcoming section.

9.1.1. Past external events

The table below (Table 7) provides a list of past external events, for M19 – M30 of the project, in which ACCEPT partners took part representing the consortium.

Table 7: Participation in external events M19 - M30

Event Name	Date(s)	Location	Link
Pint of Science 2023	24.05.2023	Spain	https://pintofscience.es/
Enlit Europe 2022	29/11-1/12/2022	Frankfurt, Germany	https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/news-events/events/european-sustainable-energy-week-2022-2022-09-26_en
EUSEW - EU Sustainable Energy Week 2022	26.09.2022	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.enlit-europe.com/2022-edition

In addition, the participation to BRIDGE is a high priority event for the dissemination of all ACCEPT outputs. The ACCEPT project is part of the BRIDGE initiative, with representatives in the Data Management, Business Models, Consumer and Citizen Engagement and Regulation Working Groups. Moreover, the ACCEPT project has agreed to actively participate in Action 3 of the Data Management WG, looking at the interoperability of flexibility assets, and co-chair the Business Models Working Group.

ACCEPT partners have been active in different BRIDGE working groups, meetings and have also participated to the BRIDGE General Assembly 2023. All the BRIDGE activities are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Participation in BRIDGE Meetings M19 - M30

Meeting	Attendees	Date
BRIDGE SG Indicators meeting	EEE, SIN	07 th July 2022
BRIDGE WG Meeting – Consumer and Citizen Engagement	EEE	1 st March 2023
BRIDGE SG Indicators meeting	EEE, SIN	18 th August 2023
BRIDGE SG Indicators meeting	EEE, SIN	28 th November 2023
BRIDGE General Assembly 2023	EEE, HYP, IsZEB	29 th – 30 th March 2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG KoM (2022-2023)	HYP, IsZEB	22 nd September 2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG – Action 5	HYP	18 th November 2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG	HYP, IsZEB	9 th December 2022
BRIDGE Data Management WG – Action 3	HYP	30 th January 2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG – Action 3	HYP	17 th February 2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG – Action 5	HYP	28 th February 2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG – Action 3	HYP	6 th March 2023
BRIDGE Data Management WG KoM (2023 – 2024)	HYP	28 th of June 2023

In addition, ACCEPT has supported the Case Study survey #8 on “Best practices on citizen consumer engagement”.

10. Synergies with other EU projects

Synergies with other EU projects are part of WP 10, since it is also part of the dissemination & communication of the project, a brief outlook on the activities follows:

One of the main pathways for disseminating the key outcomes and learning points of ACCEPT, as well as gaining useful insights into what other EU projects are currently doing in the space of energy communities, demand flexibility and consumer-centric energy services to assist with the energy transition, is the establishment of strategic synergies with similar EU projects, as well as participating in the BRIDGE initiative.

With regards to the establishment of key synergies with other projects, ACCEPT is part of a ‘focus group’ with the projects HESTIA, SENDER, ReDREAM and iFLEX, all funded under the same H2020 call. The ‘focus group’ is discussing common challenges, exchanging experiences, lessons learned and best practices under specific thematic meetings organized on an ad-hoc, yet regular, basis.

Within the frame of the “Sustainable Places 2022” event, a common workshop was organized with the title “Fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility” (see also Figure 27), to offer the opportunity to give an overview on the status and experiences on user engagement within the pilot sites of the five sister projects and for knowledge exchange in order to improve the implemented strategies, tools and platforms. The workshop was held on 08th September 2022 in a hybrid format and represented a great opportunity for the ‘focus group’ on sharing their experiences, findings and results when implementing the project activities at the pilot sites.

Figure 27: Hybrid workshop organized at the Sustainable Places 2022 event.

Based on the success of the workshop at SP2022 the sister projects ACCEPT, HESTIA, ReDREAM, SENDER and iFLEX have organized a next workshop for the Sustainable Places 2023 event with the title “Innovative solution and co-creation for effective implementation of demand response”, to intensify the collaboration. Within the workshop of SP2023 on 14th June 2023 in Madrid, Spain, the sister projects have mainly addressed user outreach and engagement as the key drivers for innovation of digital and technology-based demand response solutions. The projects have presented their co-creation activity findings from the involved pilot sites, and discussed impacts that the energy crisis is having or will have on user engagement.

Figure 28: Hybrid workshop organized at the Sustainable Places 2023 event.

The collaboration with sister projects will also be reflected in a white paper on 'Fostering user engagement for reliable demand response flexibility' that is under preparation and where each of the projects contribute with its experience. For the white paper creation, regular web-meetings are organized.

There are also synergies developed with the SCORE project under the framework of EC's Horizon Results Booster (HRB). The ACCEPT project participated on a Survey for potential synergies with the participating projects (module A) and the results were integrated into the final report. The next survey starts in Juli "module B - Helping projects from the portfolio to design and execute a portfolio dissemination plan".

There are also different collaboration activities of ACCEPT project partners with other H2020 projects, like e.g. UCC shared ACCEPT outputs with the H2020 ENCLUDE and EUB SuperHub as part of its collaboration and learning activities in other H2020 projects.

11. Outreach on pilot site level

11.1. Living Lab Branding

For the best possible stakeholder engagement within the 4 Pilot Sites of the project, the consortium decided to create an individual branding for each Living Lab, based on the LL Partner's corporate Identity in national language. The main task was to create communication material in the partners design while still have the visual & contextual connection to the ACCEPT project. The focus was on the value propositions of the different services tested in each demo from the customer's perspective.

- **Aspra Spitia:** Greece/ Greek
- **Culemborg:** Netherlands/ Dutch
- **Murcia:** Spain/Spanish
- **Massagno:** Switzerland/Italian

Figure 29: Living Lab Leaflet Aspra Spitia / Greece.

Figure 30: Living Lab Leaflet Culemborg / Netherlands.

Figure 31: Living Lab Leaflet Murcia / Spain.

Figure 32: Living Lab Leaflet Massagno / Switzerland

11.2. Pilot Site Activity

Pilot site activities are carried out within WP3 (Task 3.1 & 3.4) but are also part of WP9 as important aspect for dissemination and communication activities for enabling a smooth operation of the pilot sites. The activities within the pilot sites are summarized in D3.5 – Report on citizen recruitment activity outcome and D3.7 – Consumer engagement and design validation roadmap.

12. Monitoring & Evaluation

12.1. Activity schedule

The following table gives a detailed overview of the planned dissemination and communication activities within the ACCEPT project. This plan will be the guideline and basis for evaluation for all dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime.

Table 9: Dissemination and communication activity schedule

Activity	Schedule	Responsibility
Project website	M1-M3: Design and Development of the project's website	EEE
	M4-M42: Regular update of the website content	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Social media	M1-M2: Setup of social media channels	EEE
	M2-M42: Constant social media activity according to social media activity plan	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Scientific publications	M6-M42	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Workshops	M6-M42	All Partners
Electronic newsletters	M6-M42 Bi-Annual Issue	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Press releases	M1-M42	All Partners
Dissemination material	M7: General project Leaflet created	EEE
	M6: Leaflets for stakeholder engagements within the Living Labs created	EEE Contribution: all Partners
	M6-M10 Project Rollup & Poster	EEE
Participation in external events	M1-M42	EEE & Hypertech Contribution: all Partners
Project presentation	M1-M3	EEE
Project video / slideshow	M6-M32 1 initial version + update	EEE Contribution: all Partners
Trainings / webinars	M12-M42	All Partners
Presentation & feedback session	M6-M42	All Partners

12.2. Monitoring of dissemination and communication activities

The dissemination and communication activities during the project lifetime will be regularly monitored in order to enable and adequately evaluate the communication performance of the consortium. The monitoring of the performed dissemination and communication activities carried out by the ACCEPT project partners is not only important as the progress can be documented, but also to initiate countermeasures in case of not fulfillment of the planned target values. Those target values, as basis for the evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities, are represented by special KPIs that indicate a qualitative and quantitative evaluation. The progress of activities and the fulfillment of the different KPIs will be reported in each of the updated versions of the DCP.

Date [DD/MM/YYYY]	Description (location, title of event, the main content of the message, etc.)	Estimated number of persons reached
24/10/2020	Milestone participation in ongoing and upcoming EU Projects and reference to the input	General Site Statistics during 2019 - 1 219 549 Users & 10 160 812 Site Reach
04/01/21	IN2ES participacion en ACCEPT project, description of project and its objectives and link to ACCEPT website	765
19/01/2021	description of the project in our website and link to ACCEPT web	966
20/01/2021	post on facebook, "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	49
20/01/2021	Post on twitter "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	566
20/01/2021	Post on linkedin "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	335
20/01/2021	Post on instagram: "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	586
20/01/2021	MiEnergia formará parte del proyecto ACCEPT	1236
20/01/2021	Post on twitter "Un gran paso para el desarrollo de las comunidades energéticas." linked to blog	85
16/02/2021	Post on linkedin "El equipo del proyecto Accept está formado por 18 socios de 9 países de la Unión Europea" linked to blog	58
16/02/2021	Post on twitter "El equipo del proyecto Accept está formado por 18 socios de 9 países de la Unión Europea" linked to blog	44
16/02/2021	Post on Twitter	200
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia Proyectos I+D+i" Twitter (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	246
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia Proyectos I+D+i" Facebook page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	345
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia Proyectos I+D+i" LinkedIn (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	1148
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia" LinkedIn (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	49
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia" Facebook page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	345
23/03/2021	Post on "MiEnergia" Twitter page (social media plan) linked to ACCEPT web	246

Figure 33: Dissemination & Communication Monitoring tool.

The Dissemination & Communication Monitoring Tool (Figure 33) was created to ensure good and comprehensive monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities of the ACCEPT project partners. All activities that serve the outreach of project activities, results, outcomes, etc. are reported within this tool by each partner, indicating the partner institution that has executed the activity, the type of dissemination and communication action (web article, social media post, participation to workshop/event/conference, etc.) when the activity was carried out, including description, link, targeted audience, etc. The D&C monitoring tool was provided to all the project partners by uploading it on the ACCEPT repository. All partners are responsible for regularly including their activities in the monitoring tool and EEE is monitoring on regular basis the progress of activities.

12.3. Performance & KPIs

The following table shows the summary chart of ACCEPT Dissemination and Communication activities measured with respective KPIs.

Table 10: Dissemination and Communication performance KPIs

Communication & Dissemination Supports and Channels	KPIs	Main Target Stakeholders		
		Energy sector	End users	Facilitators
Project Documentation				
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates	X	O	X
Project Publications				
Project newsletter	7 (bi-annual issues) 100 Subscribers	X	X	X
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (on average)	X	O	X
Project Leaflet	1 initial version + updates 500 copies printed	X	X	O
Poster	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Rollup	1 initial version + updates	X	X	X
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	X	O	X
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	X	O	X
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	X	X	X
Pilot Site Leaflets	4 different versions	O	X	O
Online Presence				
Project website	1 website, monthly updated 5.000 visitors	X	X	X
Related websites	10+	Depending on specific website		
LinkedIn	At least 1 weekly update 150 Follower	X	X	X
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update 500 Follower	X	X	X
Youtube	50 Follower	X	X	X
Events				
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	X	X	X
Training sessions	3	X	X	X
External events	30+	Depending on specific event		

Caption:

X Main target
O Secondary target

12.1. Evaluation

Table 11: Dissemination and Communication KPI evaluation

Communication & Dissemination Supports and Channels	KPIs	Status M30
Project Documentation		
Reference PPT presentation	1 initial version + updates	1 initial version – template 1 updated version – general project ppt
Project Publications		
Project newsletter	7 (bi-annual issues) 100 Subscribers	4 Newsletters issued <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter #1 - total opens 61,4% • Newsletter #2 - total opens 79,5% • Newsletter #3 - total opens 59% • Newsletter #4 - total opens 52,2% 1 Newsletter prepared (#5) 73 Subscribers
Articles and proceedings	3 publications per year (on average)	Overall 14 publications (7 scientific)
Project Leaflet	1 initial version + updates 500 copies printed	1 initial version 1 updated version
Poster	1 initial version + updates	1 initial version 1 updated version
Rollup	1 initial version + updates	1 initial + updated version 1 second version 1 updated version of each Rollup
Project deliverables	See list of deliverables	Public Deliverables are regularly updated on the website library https://www.accept-project.eu/library
Open access repository	1 deposit per year	Zenodo is used as open access repository
Project video / slideshow	1 initial version + update	1 draft version
Pilot Site Leaflets	4 different versions	4 different versions
Online Presence		
Project website	1 website, monthly updated 5.000 visitors	1 website Total pageviews: 1080 443 website sessions 317 unique visitors
Related websites	10+	10
LinkedIn	At least 1 weekly update 150 Follower	> Weekly update 44 Posts / 237 Follower
Twitter/Facebook	At least 1 weekly update 500 Follower	> Weekly update 42 Posts / 736 Follower
Youtube	50 Follower	-
Events		
Presentation & feedback sessions	3	-
Training sessions	3	-
External events	30+	14

APPENDIX I – DOCUMENTATION OF ACCEPT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

CONFERENCES, EVENTS, WORKSHOPS, WEBINARS, THEMATIC MEETINGS

Name of event, conference, meeting	Date	Link / Comment
BRIDGE Data Management WG meeting	22.03.2022	Presentation at the Parallel Session 4.1 of the Data Management WG, in the session 'Interoperability of home appliances'
InnoGrid 2022	14.06.2022	Participation to InnoGrid 2022 conference of PP Hypertech (Online) - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InEEIWd_KOA&ab_channel=ENTSO-E-EuropeanNetworkofTransmissionSystemOperatorsforElectricity
Sustainable Places 2022 Workshop	08.09.2022	Participation to SP2022 Workshop on "Fostering User Engagement for Innovative Demand Response For Effective Flexibility" (collaborative workshop with sister projects) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dTVsj4BGaZ0&ab_channel=SustainablePlaces
Jornadas IEEE PES-VST y Cátedra Smart Cities	30.09.2022	Participation to Thematic Meeting of PP CIRCE
EUSEW 2022	26.09.2022	Participation to EUSEW 2022 of PP RINA-C
ICSC-CITIES 2022	28-30.11.2022	Participation to ICSC-CITIES 2022 conference of PP CIRCE, http://2022.icsc-cities.com/index.html
ENLIT Europe 2022	29.-30.11.2022	Participation to ENLIT 2022 of PPs Hypertech and AEM
Sister Projects Collaboration Meeting	10.01.2023	Sister projects collaboration online meeting to discuss, white paper and follow-up of SP2022 Open Letter
Sister Projects Collaboration Meeting	10.02.2023	Sister projects collaboration online meeting to discuss white paper
Sister Projects Collaboration Meeting	03.05.2023	Sister projects collaboration online meeting to discuss white paper and workshop organization at SP2023
Pint of Science 2023	24.05.2023	Participation to Pint of Science 2023 of PP CIRCE, https://pintofscience.es/
IEEE EEEIC23 + I&CPS Europe	06-09.06.2023	Participation to IEEE EEEIC23 + I&CPS Europe of PP CIRCE, https://www.eeeic.net/eeeic/
Sustainable Places 2023 Workshop	14.06.2023	Participation to SP2023 Workshop on "Innovative Solutions and Co-Creation for Effective Implementation of Demand Response"

ARTICLES PUBLISHED, PRESS COVERAGE, MEDIA

Date	Type of Publication /Article	Details (e.g., Title of the paper/DOI)	Open Access
04.02.2022	Social Media Article	Repost on Twitter on complimentary reports into current barriers facing CECs	Yes
09.05.2022	Social Media Article	Repost on Twitter on the Citizen-Application developed by CERTH	Yes
24/5/2022	Social Media Article	Repost on Twitter on the ENTSO-E InnoGrid 2022 event	Yes

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20.06.2022	Conference paper	Operationalising participation: Key obstacles and drivers to Citizen Energy Community formation in Europe's Energy Transition, https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/international-conference-on-energy-research-and-social-science	Yes
08.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on linkedin: ponencia de la solar sobre comunidades de energía	Yes
08.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on twitter: ponencia sobre comunidades de energía	Yes
08.07.2022	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	You Tube video: pòncia de La Solar sobre comunidades de energía	Yes
13.07.2022	Social Media Article	Facebook link:Impulsar el #autoconsumo #fotovoltaico bien de forma individual o colectiva sólo trae ventajas	Yes
18.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on linkedin: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en 7 TV Región de Murcia hablando sobre las comunidades de energía	Yes
18.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on twitter: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en @la7tele de Murcia hablando de las comunidades de energía	Yes
18.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facebook: Francisco Espín, miembro de nuestro consejo rector, en La 7 hablando sobre las comunidades de energía	Yes
19.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facebook: Financiado con fondos europeos, el proyecto #AcceptH2020 pretende desarrollar y ofrecer un conjunto de herramientas para que las comunidades energéticas ofrezcan servicios innovadores	Yes
19.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Instagram: Financiado con fondos europeos, el proyecto #AcceptH2020 pretende desarrollar y ofrecer un conjunto de herramientas para que las comunidades energéticas ofrezcan servicios innovadores	Yes
20.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on sustainability projects - LinkedIn	Yes
20.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on sustainability projects - Twitter	Yes
28.07.2022	Social Media Article	Francisco Espín, miembro del consejo rector de nuestra cooperativa y director de Efficiency Services Consulting presentó el proyecto "Comunidades Energéticas de la Región de Murcia" en la Federación de Municipios como parte del Proyecto #AcceptH2020	Yes
29.07.2022	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Ponencia sobre comunidades de energía	Yes
29.07.2022	Social Media Article	Twitter post: Ponencia sobre comunidsdes de energía	Yes
29.07.2022	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	You Tube video: pòncia de La Solar sobre comunidades de energía	Yes
29.07.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facebook: ponencia cambio climático	Yes
07.08.2022	Social Media Article	Facebook post: Las solar en efficiency consulting	Yes
09.08.2022	Social Media Article	LinkedIn post:La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético.	Yes
09.08.2022	Social Media Article	Twitter: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético.	Yes
09.08.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facebook: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético	Yes

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09.08.2022	Social Media Article	post on instagan: La penetración de energías renovables es imprescindible para la descarbonización del sistema energético	Yes
12.08.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facenook: Francisco Espin Sánchez, Director de proyectos de comunidades energéticas concede una entrevista a la #RevistaTécnicaIndustrial,	Yes
30.08.2022	Social Media Article	Linkedin post:Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Yes
30.08.2022	Social Media Article	Twitter post:Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Yes
30.08.2022	Social Media Article	Instagram post: Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos,	Yes
30.08.2022	Social Media Article	Facebook post: Las comunidades energéticas son iniciativas prometedoras para involucrar a los ciudadanos	Yes
07.09.2022	Social Media Article	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - Facebook	Yes
07.09.2022	Social Media Article	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - twitter	Yes
07.09.2022	Social Media Article	Post on workshop at Sustainable Places Conference - LinkedIn	Yes
27.09.2022	Social Media Article	Post On Facebook: Creemos en un planeta descarbonizado y en el que todos podamos ser autosuficientes energéticamente	Yes
27.09.2022	Social Media Article	Instagram post: Creemos en un planeta descarbonizado y en el que todos podamos ser autosuficientes energéticamente	Yes
05.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Yes
05.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Yes
05.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on the first Living Lab in Murcia	Yes
06.10.2022	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Website news on the energy saving strategies	Yes
07.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Living Labs	Yes
07.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Living Labs	Yes
09.10.2022	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Webiste news on research and development activities of AEM	Yes
21.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Instagram: Programa CE Implementa	Yes
21.10.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Programa CE Implementa para comunidades energéticas	Yes
21.10.2022	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Programa CE Implementa para comunidades energéticas.	Yes
04.11.2022	Social Media Article	Instagram post: @mejor_conectados	Yes
04.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Mejor Conectados	Yes
04.11.2022	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Mejor Conectados	Yes
04.11.2022	Social Media Article	Twitter Post: @mejorconecta2	Yes
08.11.2022	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	Website news on the advantages of energy communities	Yes
26.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post om instagram: Lideramos el proyecto #accepth2020	Yes
26.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post on facebook: Lideramos el proyecto #accepth2020	Yes
26.11.2022	Social Media Article	linkedin post: Lideramos el proyecto Accept_H2020	Yes
26.11.2022	Social Media Article	twitter post: Lideramos el proyecto @AcceptH2020	Yes

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28-30/11/2022	Scientific publication	Effect of sustainable Local Energy Communities on LV distribution networks, http://2022.icsc-cities.com/index.html	Yes
29.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Enlit event	Yes
29.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Enlit event	Yes
29.11.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Enlit event	Yes
29/11-1/12/2022	Event	Frankfurt, Germany / Enlit Europe 2022 / Booth on ACCEPT project at the EU Projects Zone	Yes
30.11.2022	Event	Frankfurt, Germany / Enlit Europe 2022 / Presentation at 'Smart and Green Energy Communities'	Yes
16.12.2022	Social Media Article	Instagram Post: El Realengo	Yes
16.12.2022	Social Media Article	post on facebook: El Realengo	Yes
16.12.2022	Social Media Article	linkedin post: El Realengo	Yes
16.12.2022	Social Media Article	twitter post: El Realengo	Yes
28.12.2022	Communication Campaign (Radio, TV, etc.)	Comunidad energética renovable Bullas: haciendo frente a la pobreza energética	Yes
28.12.2022	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Mejor Conectados	Yes
28.12.2022	Social Media Article	Instagram post: @mejor_conectados	Yes
28.12.2022	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Mejor Conectados	Yes
28.12.2022	Social Media Article	Twitter Post: Mejor Conectados	Yes
04.01.2023	Open Letter	Lessons learnt during the workshop "Empowerment of citizens: fostering user engagement for innovative demand response for effective flexibility", https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-1	Yes
10.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on 4th newsletter Facebook	Yes
10.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on 4th newsletter twitter	Yes
10.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on 4th newsletter linkedin	Yes
11.01.2023	White Paper	Smart Built4EU, Task Force 3, Topic C: Data driven indicators for smart buildings, https://smartbuilt4eu.eu/publications/	Yes
17/1/2023	Social Media Article	Post on Twitter about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Yes
17/1/2023	Social Media Article	Post on LinkedIn about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Yes
17/1/2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook about the ACCEPT Newsletter #4	Yes
18.01.2023	Social Media Article	Instagram post: Comunidades energéticas	Yes
18.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Comunicades energéticas	Yes
19.01.2023	Social Media Article	Linkedin Post: Comunidades energéticas	Yes
19.01.2023	Social Media Article	Twitter post: Comunidades energéticas	Yes
20.01.2023	Social Media Article	Instagram post: Asamblea General	Yes
20.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Asamblea General	Yes
20.01.2023	Social Media Article	Linkedin Post: Asamblea General	Yes
20.01.2023	Social Media Article	Twitter post: Asamblea General	Yes
23.01.2023	Social Media Article	LinkedIn post	Yes
27.01.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Ecomur	Yes
27.01.2023	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Ecomur	Yes
27.01.2023	Social Media Article	Twitter post: Ecomur	Yes
01.02.2023	Social Media Article	Instagram post: Diputación de Soria	Yes
01.02.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Diputación de Soria	Yes
01.02.2023	Social Media Article	Linkedin post: Diputación de Soria	Yes
01.02.2023	Social Media Article	Twitter post: Diputación de Soria	Yes
02.02.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook about last meeting	Yes
02.02.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Twitter about last meeting	Yes

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02.02.2023	Social Media Article	Post on LinkedIn about lasr meeting	Yes
14.02.2023	Social Media Article	Repost on Twitter	Yes
14.02.2023	Social Media Article	Repost on LinkedIn	Yes
01.03.2023	Journal article	Operationalizing participation: Key obstacles and drivers to citizen energy community formation in Europe's energy transition, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sctalk.2022.100104	Yes
08.03.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Prueba piloto	Yes
08.03.2023	Social Media Article	Instagram Post: Prueba Piloto	Yes
08.03.2023	Social Media Article	Twitter Post: Prueba piloto	Yes
08.03.2023	Social Media Article	Linkedin Post: Prueba Piloto	Yes
08.03.2023	Press Release	Press Release on local newspaper, https://www.laverdad.es/content-local/miwenergia-feria-plantas-solares/	Yes
20.03.2023	Social Media Article	Post on twitter about the last event	Yes
20.03.2023	Social Media Article	Post on linkedin about the last event	Yes
23.03.2023	Media (Youtube, Blog, etc.)	The EU Projects Zone Podcast / Presentation of the project	Yes
18.04.2023	Social Media Article	Post on Facebook: Hogares Autoconsumo	Yes
06-09/06/2023	Scientific publication	Initial Assessment of Electrical Flexibility of Combustion-Based District Heating Systems, https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14095.87200	Yes